

India In the Way of Viksat Bharat@ 2047**Sandeep. G. Tiwari**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17291558>**ABSTRACT:**

In the present context since 2014 government takes various initiatives inform of E-Governance has simplified a citizen interface with the government. to ensure closeness with government the government thrive to ensure benchmarking of service quality. The central government e-governance model has benefited in bringing transparency and openness to government process. To achieve the ends of Viksit Bharat @20247 it adopted of e- version 7.0 has created paperless offices in all departments in the central secretaries. In 2023, the Centralized Public Grievances Redress and Monitoring System (CPGRAMS)helped redress 21 lakh citizen grievances. In 2024 with three months from January to March it helped 9.5 lakh citizens to redress their problems. the best manifestation of Maximum Governance Minimum Government policy is a digitally empowered citizens and digitally transformed institution which is essential for development and speed disposal of public affairs.

KEYWORDS:

Structural Adjustment, Entrepreneurship, Intensive Manufacturing, Power security, Green Revolution.

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Objective of the research paper

1. To analysis the potentiality of India in production and investment.
2. The government efforts to achieve self-reliant.
3. The need of future reformation in policies.

Agricultural incentive policies and Viksit Bharat:

In the way of Viksit Bharat Indian governments since initiation of green revolution focuses on agricultural development with adoption of technology in agriculture, dairy farming, fisheries and horticulture. The agriculture still remains as the source of employment and income of majority of rural people. Its share in GDP is crucial. Thus, the India had adopted various incentive base policies to promote agriculture activities in order to sustain stable producing farming.

Governments since independence by introducing numerous policies

thrives to make agriculture as venture of income. It gives the subsidies on purchasing of fertilizers, seeds, and for other inputs in order to reduce the production cost. To mitigate the risk of collapse of income by damaging standing crops due to natural calamities, the government of India introduces crop base insurances in form of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bhima Yojana.

To save farmers from the yoke of heavy interest on loan owned by private money lenders as well as government financial institution government of India introduces 'Modified Interest Subvention Scheme (Miss). Further to promote agriculture base infrastructure it introduces 'Agriculture Infrastructure Fund (AIF)The government of India has launched the central Sector Scheme (CSS)for Formation and Promotion of 10,000 Farmer Producer Organization the year 2020.Apart from these government of India to increase extra income of farmers it introduces National bee-keeping and Honey Mission (NBHM)in 2020.

To save the farmers from the risk price fluctuation of food grains, it introduces Market Intervention Scheme and Price Support Scheme (MISPSS). All these policies of governments help to achieve Viksit Bharat by 20247 by stabilizing the income of farmers.

The foundation stone of India's Journey for Viksit Bharat laid down in structural Reforms Policy of 1991 which involves broad based deregulation, building a robust manufacturing, ensuring energy security, fostering collaboration between the private and government, competitive business environment, foreign direct investment, fair income distribution, between capital and labor. This policy of government makes India to adopt numerous future economic developmental programmers and actions.

1. Broad based de-regulation,
2. Building up the robust manufacturing base,
3. An energy transition sensitive to the needs of India.
4. Tripartite compact between the government, private sector and academia.

To achieve its first priority, the government India initiated the its effort in 1991it self this shift facilitates more business-friendly environment and attracted substantial foreign investment, accelerating economic growth. However, it is not a one and done strategy but in a continuous

process the government of India has also remained committed to over the last decade.

In 2014 several big-ticket items have been reformed, including rationalizing over 20,000 compliances, decriminalizing and removing or implying penalties in 300 laws an incentivizing business by extending unique benefit to key sectors and clusters. The present central govern after the regime of UPA I and II to remove obstacle it introduced reforms in forest regulation. Through the forest basic activities such as constructing a passageway from their property to main a main road. Other structural forms also introduced to make flexible Tax administration and transparency to control loopholes of tax escapism. To control the leverages of camouflage which helps to people of insolvency and bankruptcy. (IBC) which established a framework for dealing renewal the real estate sector (RERA) which helped clean up the real estate sector roll -out of the India Stack (UID, UPI, DBT), which has helped reduce process inefficiencies and plunge leakage.

For sustained economic growth and fostering an environment where business can thrive deregulation is crucial and critical. Earlier excessive regulation often imposes high costs on business, particularly small and medium enterprises which struggle to navigate complex administrative procedures. In 2024-2025 Economic survey Small and Medium Scale Enterprises can lose approximately 50 percent of their industrial plot to building standards while inflexible work hours prevent manufactures from meeting demand surges during festive periods.

Excessive regulation not only hampers our industries but also stifles the creation of quality human capital.

In the field of education India made a revolutionary shift toward promoting technical education and striking balance between traditional and technical education in this tandem the parliament empowers the University Grant Commission and All India Council for Technical Education regulations prevent institutions from flexible altering their course offerings for their degree programmers and adapting the education provided to changing market demands.

In the way of Viksit Bharat, the process of deregulation enhances the innovation and attracts private investment, which is essential for long-term economic resilience. It also helps to India to reduce the pressure and

scope of rent-seeking and corruption, ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently rather than being wasted on navigating regulatory red tape. By creating business friendly environment that priorities ease of doing businesses, deregulations enable industries to respond dynamically to market demands and technologically to market demands and technological advancements. Similarly entrusting our educational institutions, faculty and students to develop novel solutions to emerging challenges will only contribute to raising the overall quality of human capital by fostering a spirit of innovation and critical thinking among our youth.

Strengthening and encouraging domestic industries:

In the way of Viksit Bharat, India is home of some prominent domestic industries such as agriculture and allied sectors, manufacturing, (textile, chemicals, automobiles, engineering goods, entertainment, health care, and renewable energy etc.) these are major components for GDP thus of encouraging economic freedom of these industries through deregulation and strengthening to make a nation more attractive destination for global investment is essential in an era where global supply. In essence, sustainable and inclusive growth depends on reducing the friction that excessive regulations impose, allowing business and individuals to maximize their potential.

Manufacture strengthening:

To realize the dream of Viksit Bharat by 2047 the level of manufacturing should be increased both at the level to meet domestic need and export to earn foreign exchange. Across history, manufacturing strength has been a marker of the economic prowess of a nation. The hum of manufacturing was at the center of ancient empires such as the Chola or the Guptas medieval empires across Europe, the UK in the 19th century, and the US in the 20th century. East Asia lifted millions out of poverty, raised their standard of living, upskilled young population and absorbed them into the workforce on the back of the manufacturing wave that started in the 1970s. As a poster child of the East Asian miracle, China is expected to command a share of 45 percent of all global manufacturing, single-handedly matching or outmatching the US and its allies by 2030. In 2000, China accounted for 6% of global manufacturing three decades prior.

Secondly, manufacturing development kick-starts skilling at the

firm level. This creates dividends for poor economies that cannot afford to invest heavily in education. For instance, firms were vehicle of industrial learning in East Asia, which led these nations to tap the potential of young, unskilled demography even when resources were limited. Thirdly, a rising manufacturing sector, in turn puts pressure on the creation of hard infrastructure, smoothens governance, and reduces regulatory burdens. 19th –century England is an example of industrial growth which, in turn kick-started governance reforms. Hernando de Soto writes in his book entitled ‘The Mystery of capital’ that it was not until the industrial Revolution that the British reformed their institutions, public service delivery, and improved governance.

India has the potentiality to employ nearly 80 lakh people every year till 2030. Though government of India has recognized the manufacturing sector potentiality notably in Micro, Medium and Small enterprises. In reducing external dependencies and employment generation. This is reflected in the host of manufacturing –specific and allied sector policies to incentives higher domestic production. Credit constraints for MSMEs have been eased through initiatives like the credit guarantee scheme for MSEs and Tred’s (Trade Receivables Discounting Systems) facilitating Rs 1.38 lakh crore in financing as of FY24. The newly introduced ULI aims to lower credit costs through real-time risk assessment. Infrastructure advancement have also played play a crucial role. With the median turn-around time at Indian ports having between 2014 and 2024, making them more efficient than those in the US, Australia, and Singapore. This efficiency gain is reflected in India’s rise in the World Bank’s Logistics Performance Index, climbing from 54th place in 2014 to 38th in 2023.

Industrial Policy, deployment of labor and capital

Along with PLIs the government of India by accessing the deployment of labor and capital as important, it in this tandem formulates the right industrial policy to balance between deployment of labor and capital is important. To achieve the dream of VIKSIT Bharat it is inevitable to nation to take demographic advantage, with a high proportion of youth, lab our –intensive growth is critical to ensure mass employment and social stability. However, this does not mean that technology –intensive growth should be disregarded. Technology –intensive industries can and must complement labor-intensive sectors rather than replace them entirely. Labors –intensive sector can absorb the large workforce while technol-

ogy is leveraged to enhance manufacturing, logistics and supply chain efficiency without displacing jobs outright. Combined with systemic deregulation across sectors, this will create a viable India's SMEs sector.

Energy Security for Viksit Bharat:

The transition both in climate change and green energy demonstrably affect India's economic growth. The government of India perused green energy enhancement policies from western countries. India has to secure tradition energy manufacturing units along with adoption of modern green energy production center. Rush to transition away from fossil fuels, many developed economies have prematurely shut down conventional power plants without securing reliable and affordable alternatives. For instance, presently Europe struggled with an energy crisis exacerbated by geo-political factors and policy missteps, highlighting the risk of an abrupt transition without a robust framework for energy security. India as a rapid growing economy, it must not be experienced such loopholes which are witnessed by Europe.

As economic historian Prof. Peter Temin argued, "modern technology has extended the innovations of the Industrial Revolution in the context of high wages and cheap power. However, these factor prices are not typical in many areas of Africa and Asia and modern technology is not as profitable there as in other higher -wage parts of the world" thinking about high wage and cheap power refers both utilization of human and natural resources in order to ensure stable increase in per capita and industrialization with abundant availability of power or energy to run energy at cheap cost. India has to build the energy infrastructure in the way united states which provide cheap power to robust manufacturing abundantly in all season. (V. Anantha Nageswaran, 'Roadmap for Viksit Bharat@2027'' Yojana, March 2025 P-7.

India by giving its due concentration on carbon emission it remains on third place on per-capita carbon emission in the world. Amid the competition on industrial growth with developed countries gives the high priority for renewable energy storage. But sufficient flow of green compensative fund from developed countries is the need of hour for developing countries like India. but in the name of political sovereignty and liberalism developed countries camouflage the reality greenhouse impact on developing country economy. Unlike western country, India comprehen-

sively relied on subsidy policy and financial market to support energy transition, which increase its expenditure for renewable energy from 3.7 % to 5.6 of GDP.

Effort through the Budget or fiscal policies for Viksit Bharat:

Viksit Bharat @2027 aims to make India a developed nation with economic growth, environmental sustainability social progress and good governance. To achieve this end the government of India with state governments thrives to provide stable income to people by introducing various plans and programmers for women empowerment, employability opportunity, reform in agriculture etc.,

Atman Ibhhar Bharat in Defense in the way of Viksit Bharat:

In the 2023–24 financial year India's domestic defense production reached Rs 1.27 lakh crore, marking a record high, with an impressive increase of approximately 174% from 46.429 crore in 2014–2015. India is on track to achieve a target of 1.75 crore in defense production in the current financial year by 2029 further establishing. India aims at to reach Rs 3lakh crore in defense production by 2029, further establishing itself as a global defense manufacturing hub. India's defense exports have surged from Rs 1941 crore in FY 2014–2015 to Rs 21,083 crore in FY 2023–2024 reflecting a remarkable increase in export value. Defense exports have grown by 21 times from Rs 4312 crore in 2004–2014 decade to 88,319 crores in the 2024 to 24 decades. Driven by government policy reforms, ease of doing business initiatives and a push for self-reliance, India now export over 100 nations.

Conclusion:

The dream of Viksit Bharat neither miracle nor dream, it is process of economic policy making, implementation, investment, financial assistance for premierships, efforts for self-reliant in food grains, science technology, capital investment. India Since Independence governments are trying to development in agriculture infrastructure, road and transformation, promotion of indigenouse technology in production, science and technology. Reformation in taxes policies with promotion of exports to maintain balance. To rapid disposal of public grievance governments have taken the comprehensive policies to digitalization of services.

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The Authors have no conflict of interest to declare that they are relevant to the content of this article.

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